

1 On the interaction of wind waves and seamounts

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16 17 Abstract

18
19 Seamounts are a prominent feature of the ocean, whose interest concerns both their origin (see
20 the recent paper by French and Romanowicz, 2015) and their interaction with the ocean that
21 surrounds them (Chen et al., 2015). Along this second line of interest we move towards the top of
22 these mountains. In particular we focus on their interaction with wind generated waves. Of the
23 many topographic features of different genesis that are ubiquitous in the oceans we are
24 particularly interested in those with relatively shallow summits that can interact with waves.
25 Especially long waves crossing the oceans (swells) and stormy seas are able to affect the water
26 column up to a considerable depth and therefore interact with these deep sea features. We
27 quantify this interaction through synthetic experiments using a numerical wave model (SWAN),
28 in which a simply shaped seamount is exposed to waves of different length. The results show a
29 strong interaction that leads to significant changes in the wave field, creating wake zones and
30 regions of large wave amplification. Potentially important for navigation and erosion processes,
31 mutatis mutandis these results can also be applied to emerged islands and sand banks in shelf
32 seas.

33 34 1 – Seamounts and waves

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36 Seamounts are a prominent feature of the oceans whose interest concerns both their origin (see
37 the recent paper by French and Romanowicz, 2015) and their interaction with the ocean that
38 surrounds them (Chen et al., 2015). On this second line of interest we move closer to surface and
39 analyze how sea waves interact with the top of these mountains. The interaction of sea waves and
40 bottom topography brings about many processes whose characteristics and importance are fully
41 determined by those of the sea bottom (depth, dimensions, shape, material et al.) and of the
42 impinging waves (basically wave height, period, direction, more in general the spectrum). The
43 interaction affects the two parts, the wave field being perturbed with potentially large spatial
44 gradients, while the bottom is subject to different dynamical forces and their consequent effects.
45 Apart from the continental shelves and, more so, the coastal zones, which are the center of
46 attention of a continuous flow of research and literature (e.g., Goda 2009; Nielsen 2009;
47 Davidson-Arnott, 2009; Short and Woodroffe 2009; Babanin et al., 2005), in this paper we focus
48 our attention on the deep sea, in particular on the seamounts whose top, still below the surface, is

49 however within reach of the wave effects. More specifically we analyze how the surface wave
50 field is modified by the presence of a shallow summit.

51
52 Seamounts have heights and dimensions covering a very wide range. Notwithstanding the
53 specific meteo-oceanographic action present on a narrow vertical range across the sea surface,
54 there is a dense continuity of geological features whose peak is just within this range. Shipping
55 experience and modern instruments have revealed a plethora of seamounts whose top is, in
56 marine terms, very close to the surface (e.g., Yesson et al., 2011; Wessel et al., 2010; Kearey et
57 al., 2009; Keating et al., 1987; Sinton, 1989). As a few examples we quote the Bowie and Cobb
58 seamounts in the gulf of Alaska (with summit depth of 24 and 34 m respectively), the Muirfield
59 seamount in the Indian Ocean (18 m), the Kawachi volcano (20 m) in the Solomon islands, and
60 the Socotra Rock, also called Ieodo or Parangdo (4.6 m below the surface in the Yellow Sea).

61
62 As for wind waves, they are the most ubiquitous phenomenon on the sea surface. Generated by
63 wind, developing, where wind supports, into potentially tremendous storms, they then propagate
64 on the ocean for long distance with very low loss of energy. The decrease of wave height with
65 distance is mainly due to the radial dispersion and to the different propagation speed with wave
66 period (hence length). The result is the classical swell that is an almost permanent feature of the
67 tropical zone.

68
69 Because long swell attenuates, in time and space, much less than short waves, and because the
70 longer the waves the deeper their effects are felt (see Section 2), for our experiments we focus
71 mainly on relatively long waves, up to 20 second period, a relatively large period, but also a
72 common feature in the oceans. Seamounts have the most diverse shapes. To illustrate the
73 potential effect of a seamount on the surface wave field we have chosen a simple pre-established
74 shape (Section 3) suitable to evaluate the variety of implications for the surface wave fields. The
75 analysis of the results in Section 4 provides a general feeling of the possible notable wave height
76 enhancements a passing vessel may experience on the surface. The geometrical distribution and
77 the enhancement and attenuation patterns depend on, for a given seamount, on the wavelength
78 (hence its period). Should we deal with a storm we would have a full spectrum and the overall
79 pattern would be the superposition of the modifications for the single wave components with
80 different directions and frequencies. We conclude in Section 5 with a discussion, showing how
81 most of the reported results can be applied also to the case of islands or shallow banks. We like to
82 stress how part of our “modern” results, applied to also emerged islands, have been for centuries
83 common knowledge in the Pacific islands whose inhabitants used, and still use, the resulting long
84 distance wave patterns to navigate without instruments from island to island across large spaces
85 of the ocean (Lewis, 1994).

86 87 **2 – The wave conditions and their effects below the surface**

88
89 There is an infinite variety of the seamount geometry and wave conditions we can find in the
90 oceans. We focus here on a simplified solution suitable for better understanding their interaction
91 and the related physical aspects. In this section we give a brief overview of the wave
92 characteristics relevant to this interaction.

93
94 In the most general terms the wave conditions in a certain area and at a given time are described
95 by the wave spectrum (see, e.g., Holthuijsen, 2007 for an exhaustive, but simple, description). In
96 practice we consider the sea surface as the superposition (Pierson and Marks, 1952) of a large

97 number of sinusoidal waves, each characterized by its height, direction and period (hence
98 wavelength and frequency). For our purposes we focus on a much simpler and effective
99 situation, consisting on a nearly monochromatic (i.e. single sinusoidal) wave train. This simple
100 configuration is important to understand the primary wave-bottom and wave-wave interactions.
101 In the presence of a submerged obstruction the wave field gets disturbed, giving origin to sub-
102 harmonic components that in turn may interact among themselves. In reality, the incoming wave
103 field can be composed by several different wave trains moving into different directions, so the
104 interaction gets more complex. Nevertheless, real swell trains do not depart much from the
105 monochromatic description, and given their relatively large periods, they are the ones most
106 effectively interacting with submerged bathymetry features.

107
108 Given a wave with height H and period T , there is an associated orbital motion at the surface
109 whose velocity is $u=\pi H/T$. This motion attenuates with depth z (considered negative downwards)
110 according to

$$111 \quad u_z = \frac{\pi H}{T} e^{kz} \quad (1)$$

112 with $k=2\pi/L$ the wave number and wavelength L given by

$$113 \quad L = \frac{g}{2\pi} T^2 \quad (2)$$

114
115 g is the gravity acceleration (see Holthuijsen, 2007, for a full documentation). Waves attenuate
116 rapidly with depth. From (1) it is straightforward to see that at a depth equal to half the
117 wavelength a wave, hence its orbital motion, are reduced to 4% of their surface value. However,
118 the wavelengths present in the ocean (see Table 1) and the proximity of many seamounts to the
119 surface clearly point to possible strong interactions. When waves are long enough to “feel” the
120 bottom, their attenuation is less rapid with depth. Relevant for our purpose is also the speed with
121 which waves advance, this one too decreasing when moving from deep to shallow water. This
122 implies that, coming across a sloping surface, different parts of the wave front will have different
123 speeds, and therefore the wave will tend to turn. Entering shallow water implies also, because of
124 different speeds, an increase of the wave height (at first contact there can be a decrease, but this
125 is irrelevant for our purposes).

126
127 The above provides the essential information for properly interpreting the later results. For the
128 practical tests we have used SWAN, an advanced wave model amply cited in the literature (see,
129 among others, Booij et al., 1996, and again Holthuijsen, 2007). For 2D simulations, the input
130 wave fields needs to cover the full 2D wave spectrum considering a large number of frequencies,
131 typically 30 or 36, from 0.03 to 0.5 Hz, and a large number of directions distributed on the whole
132 circle. Therefore we have complemented the single sinusoidal wave with a narrow spectral
133 Gaussian shape centered on the selected frequency (i.e. period). For the practical computation the
134 wave direction is from West to East, also narrowly distributed around the main direction, with
135 spectral resolution at 2 degree interval. The overall energy corresponds to one meter significant
136 wave height. For different experiments we consider seven different periods from 8 to 20 seconds
137 at 2 seconds interval (see Table 1 providing also the corresponding wavelengths in deep water
138 conditions).

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141 The grid for the numerical simulations is 40 km wide (North to South) and 80 km long (West to
 142 East) at 100 m interval. The wave input conditions are uniform at the West border (see Section 3
 143 for the general grid used for computation). The seamount is centered at position (0., 0.). Of the
 144 various processes that concur to the evolution of a wave field we have considered advection,
 145 refraction, shoaling, breaking (deep water and bottom induced), triad wave-wave interactions.
 146 We deal only with swell conditions, hence no wind input and fourth order nonlinear interactions
 147 have been taken into consideration. Finally, we look only for stationary states, i.e. for
 148 equilibrium conditions, hence no evolution in time is considered.

149

150 3 – Bathymetry

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152 The overall bathymetry consists of a flat deep bottom where the sea mount has been imposed.
 153 We have parameterized the seamount as a 2-D Gaussian function submerged at different levels.
 154 The function describing the bathymetry is given by

155

$$z(r) = A \left(e^{-\frac{r^2}{\lambda}} - 1 \right) - z_0 \tag{3}$$

156

157 where $z(r)$ is the water depth as a function of the distance r from the center of the seamount ($r^2 =$
 158 $x^2 + y^2$). A is a constant that defines the vertical dimension of the seamount (700m). The parameter
 159 λ is introduced to control the horizontal configuration of the seamount potentially exposed to
 160 waves. In this case a constant diameter of 8 km is set at 100 m water depth in all cases. z_0
 161 specifies the depth d of the seamount summit which ranges from 20 to 60 m (see Figure 1 and
 162 Table 2).

163

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165 Figure 1. Seamount configuration. 0 depth indicates the water surface. The different lines
 166 indicate the different bathymetry scenarios used for the summit depth

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Table 1 – Deep water wavelength for waves of different period

period (s)	8	10	12	14	16	18	20
wavelength (m)	100	156	225	306	400	506	625

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Table 2. Seamount bathymetry parameters

	A	λ ($\times 10^3$)	z_o (m)
Case 1	700	13.2	20
Case 2	700	15.2	30
Case 3	700	17.8	40
Case 4	700	21.6	50
Case 5	700	27.2	60

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4 – Results

4.1 – Physics and details of the interactions

For a better grasp of the overall results and of the various reasons behind them, we first focus on a single case, detailing the implied physics. On this basis it will be easier to get a better understanding of the overall and possible processes at work.

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Figure 2. Significant wave height (top panels) and mean wave period (lower panels) fields around the seamount for a background homogeneous input wave field of $H_s=1\text{m}$ and $T_m=20\text{s}$. The seamount summit water depth is 20m. Red colors indicate enhancement, blue colors indicate decrease of the wave field parameters compared to the input at the boundary.

188 To start with, we focus on the most prominent case, obviously the shallowest seamount (top at
189 -20 m depth) and the longest waves ($T=20$ s). Figure 2 shows the corresponding results for the
190 significant wave height H_s (top panels, a) and c)) and the mean period (lower panels, b) and d)).
191 Panels c) and d) cover the whole computational grid, 80 km in x (East) direction (the one of
192 propagation of the incoming waves), 40 km in the y (North) direction. The top of the seamount is
193 at position (0., 0.). Panels a) and b) focus around this point.

194
195 In panel a) we see the large increase of H_s just behind (1 km eastwards of) the seamount summit.
196 As a matter of fact the maximum enhancement is much larger, 3.27 m, than what visible in the
197 plot (2.4 m). The fact is that the corresponding area is very small (there are very large spatial
198 gradients). On a general perspective we find a growing wave height while waves approach the
199 seamount (from the West). This is due to shoaling occurring when the long waves feel the
200 decreasing depth on the west side of the seamount. Possibly more surprising at a first look are the
201 two lobes of large wave height, on the East side of the seamount, that protrude respectively in the
202 North and South directions. The explanation is given in the 3-D representation of Figure 3.
203 Granted that the dimensions are stretched for a better grasping of the situation, we see that, while
204 shoaling during their approach to the seamount, the waves, e.g. on the South side respect to the
205 submerged peak (negative y in panel 2a) feel a sloping bottom on their left side. This leads to a
206 drastic refraction counterclockwise that results in the northward lobe seen in the same panel.
207 Clearly there is a symmetry with respect to the $y=0$ x -axis, so we find also a clockwise turning of
208 the $y>0$ approaching waves leading to the southward lobe. It is the combination of these two
209 systems that leads to the peak (3.27 m) that, hinted to in Figure 2a, we see better in Figure 3.
210 This double drastic deviation of wave energy off the main direction is not without consequences.
211 In fact we see in Figure 2a, more extensively in 2b and also in Figure 3, the large extended area
212 of reduced wave height on the lee (eastward) side of the seamount position. Note that we are
213 used to expect lower wave heights on the lee of an island because this creates a physical block.
214 However, in our present case the lower H_s behind the seamount are due to the refraction induced
215 by the shallow local bathymetry and the consequent deviation of the flowing energy off the
216 original direction. Note also that the shadowed area extends well beyond the 40 km considered in
217 the computational grid. A first-hand estimate suggests it may extend, with a progressively
218 decreasing effect, for hundreds of kilometers. This is due to the swell conditions (very narrow
219 directional spectrum – see Section 2) we have selected for the tests. A wind sea, under active
220 generation, with its wider spectrum both in frequency and direction, would lead to a much
221 shorter wake because the lateral, off the main direction, components would soon advect energy
222 in the area behind the seamount.

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224 The fact of using an, although narrow, spectrum as input wave conditions highlights well, in
225 Figures 2b and 2d, the different refraction effects on the waves with different period, hence
226 wavelength. This is easily recognized in Figure 2b showing the distribution of the dominant
227 wave period in the various areas of the grid. We recognize at once the two pronounced lobes,
228 pointing respectively to North and South, with a longer period, 21-22 seconds, respect to the
229 central one of the impinging waves. The reason is that the various wave components in the
230 considered spectrum have different frequencies, hence wavelengths. This leads to a selective
231 refraction effect, more intense for the longer (lower frequency, longer period) waves. Of course
232 this implies that, at least for a while, we find higher frequency (lower period) waves in the lee of
233 the seamount.

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Figure 3 – An ideal 3D view of the waves impinging on a submerged seamount. Note the splitting of the incoming wave system into different ones moving in different directions.

4.2 – Overall results

The maximum significant wave heights reached for the single combinations of wave period and depth of seamount top are provided in Table 3. Remember that for all cases the input wave height is 1 m. As expected, the enhancement decreases with decreasing wave period (hence wavelength) and with the depth of the seamount. However, it is still remarkable (more or less doubling the wave energy) for waves of 10-12 seconds (a relatively short period in the oceans) and 50-60 meter depth.

Table 3. Maximum Significant wave height over the computational grid (in meters) for different summit depths and wave conditions ($T_{m-1,0}$)

$T_{m-1,0}$	20 m	30 m	40 m	50 m	60 m
8s	1.75	1.38	1.16	1.06	1.02
10s	2.03	1.82	1.55	1.35	1.21
12s	2.21	2.06	1.89	1.70	1.53
14s	2.46	2.22	2.09	1.96	1.82
16s	2.74	2.44	2.25	2.13	2.02
18s	3.03	2.67	2.44	2.28	2.17
20s	3.27	2.87	2.61	2.43	2.30

Figure 4 - Maximum Significant wave height over the computational grid for the different scenarios (see Table 3).

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257 In Figure 4 we try to give a better perception of the trends with period and depth, and of the
 258 position of the seamount at which we find the maximum wave height. For each combination of
 259 period and depth we plot in Figure 4 the maximum H_s obtained over the whole computational
 260 grid, and its position (kilometers off the center). The continuous lines show how, for a given
 261 depth, the results vary with the wave period. The dotted lines refer to a given period and show
 262 how the results change with depth. Note how in this case the lines are asymptotic to the unitary x
 263 axis while the seamount effects decrease for increasing depth. This happens at a different rate
 264 depending on the period, till disappearing when the submerged top is out of the range of action
 265 of the surface waves. A quick estimate based on the respective wavelengths suggests that the
 266 minimum 1.02 value in Figure 4 is reached for a 20 second wave when the seamount top is at
 267 about 600 meter depth.

268

269 We complement the results in Figures 3 and 4 and Table 3 showing in Figure 5, panels a) b) c),
 270 the distribution of the wave heights along the x axis, from -10 till 20 kilometers before and after
 271 the top, for three different depths (20, 30, 50 m) and all the considered periods. We will come
 272 back later to panel d). Note that the same vertical and horizontal scales have been used for the
 273 three panels. We recognize at once as, for each depth, the enhancement decreases moving to
 274 shorter (lower period) waves. Also the spatial scale, in x direction, of the changes is longer. As
 275 explained in the previous subsection, this is due to the different refraction magnitudes, stronger
 276 for longer waves, hence to a location of the maximum, as all the follow-up in the shadow zone,
 277 closer to the top position. For a similar reason, but related to a lower refraction for deeper
 278 seamounts, lower enhancements, also moving progressively to higher x positions, are found
 279 passing from a) to b), and then to c).

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Figure 5. Significant wave height profile along the $y=0$ axis for period from 8s to 20s, for different depths (20, 30, 50 m in panels (a) (b) (c) respectively. Panel (d) refers to the special case of 10 m summit depth and a 4 m significant wave height impinging on the seamount. The dash line indicates the magnitude of the input background field.

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From a more utilitarian point of view it has been suggested for wave energy harvesting or simply for coastal surfing or protection (e.g., Hanley et al., 2013; Langhamer et al., 2010; Jackson et al., 2005), to take advantage of a natural, or to build an artificial, dune on the bottom to focus, exactly for the described processes, the wave energy towards a specific position. A suitable machine there located would produce up to an order of magnitude more energy than if facing the undisturbed field. Apart of the difficulty of dealing with wave systems refracted in completely different directions, a substantial problem would be the drastic change of the maximum energy position as a function of the dominant period of the incoming waves. Of course we could plan on the base of the most common conditions (or the most energetic ones), but the overall efficiency would be highly degraded.

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299
 300 Figure 6 - Cross sections of the wave power field (kW/m) across different transects of the spatial
 301 domain.

302
 303 From more or less this perspective we show in Figure 6 the wave energy flux (from West to East)
 304 across the ± 20 km of the y axis at different x positions. The case considered is the $d = 20$ m, $T = 20$
 305 s. Starting from the uniform distribution before feeling the slopes of the seamount ($x = -10$ km),
 306 we find above the summit ($x = 0$) the strong peak due to both shoaling and refraction with on the
 307 sides a limited decrease due to the refracting components (hence not moving perpendicularly to
 308 the y axis. Moving to higher x positions, we come across the extended shadow, or wake, zone.
 309 Note the slight increase towards the larger (absolute) y values, associated to the refracted waves,
 310 skewed with respect to, but with still a component in, the x direction. As a final note we point out
 311 how the energy contribution in the $x > 0$ section is part of the one originally approaching the
 312 seamount on a $x < 0$ position.

313
 314 Having provided a physical description of the possible situations and of the reasons behind, we
 315 can better interpret the 2D wave spectra shown in Figure 7. The radial axis goes from 0. (center)
 316 till 0.15 Hz, the flow directions are shown with a Cartesian convention, this is 0° is East
 317 (consistent with the incoming wave direction) with the angle increasing counterclockwise. The
 318 energy isolines are scaled on the maximum of each single plot. The specific positions and the H_s
 319 associated to the spectrum are indicated in each panel. The case considered is again $d = 20$ m,
 320 $T = 20$ s with the purpose of highlighting the various changes.

321

Figure 7 - Wave spectra at different points of the simulation domain. The radial axis indicates flow direction in Cartesian coordinates (0° corresponds to East). $H_s = 1\text{m}$, $T_m = 20$, summit depth is 20m.

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327 In Figure 7a we see the approaching spectrum, representing the assigned wave conditions. The
328 spectrum is centered at 0.05 Hz and flowing in the x direction (angle $\theta=0$). At $x=-0.5$ km, Figure
329 7b, we already perceive a slight enlargement of the spectrum, with a consequent limited decrease
330 of its peak value, now $0.36 \text{ m}^2\text{s}$. When centered on the seamount (7c) the peak value has grown
331 because of shoaling while refraction is beginning to widen the directional distribution. The two
332 refracted systems are well evident in Figure 7d, 1.2 km after the top. Note how distributing the
333 overall available energy on a wider ($f-\theta$) zone leads to a lower spectral peak notwithstanding its
334 increased integral value ($H_s = 3.3$ m). Figures 7e and 7f show the spectra at two symmetrical
335 ($y=\pm 1$ km) positions, 2.4 kilometer after the top. We recognize the two refracting system, each
336 now not symmetrical because off the x axis. Finally, in Figures 7g and 7h we show the spectra
337 far in the wake zone. The further we go, the more the system converges towards the x direction
338 because of the more close-to- x rays pointing from the seamount position towards the considered
339 point.

340

341 As a final test we have considered the case of a much more energetic wave system, 4 meter high,
342 approaching the seamount, and assuming for this a more shallow top, at 10 meter depth. The
343 results for the different wave periods are given in Figure 4d. We note first the double H_s peak, the
344 first one associated to shoaling, the second higher one (almost 9 meter high) due to the two
345 refracted converging systems. The peak H_s values decrease with wave period, but not as much as
346 in the previous cases. For 20 and 8 seconds, the maximum H_s are close to 9 and 7 m respectively,
347 while in Figure 4a we find corresponding 3.3 and 1.75 m. This explains why we selected a one
348 meter wave for our tests, the reason being to avoid too large wave heights leading to breaking
349 that could impede a proper interpretation of the results. Indeed in the 4 m case there is a lot of
350 breaking going on at the convergence of the two systems, and it is this breaking that limits the
351 maximum wave height reachable just behind the top position.

352

353 **5 – A summary view**

354

355 The results reported in the previous section are quite robust, and they cover a wide range of
356 practical possibilities. Truly enough, they have been obtained with a series of idealized cases.
357 Any real case, with true wave spectra and its own peculiar bathymetry, would have its
358 characteristics, with enhancements and wake zones of different amplitude and extension.
359 However, by and large, and mainly for their physical interpretation, our results provide a solid
360 reference for the possible wave heights and their distribution on the sea surface. Taking into
361 account that one meter wave height is an underestimate of the average wave height in the oceans
362 (2 meter is a more realistic value), it is clear that, wherever shallow seamounts are present, the
363 wave conditions can indeed be very peculiar. Also the 4 meter case is not an unusual event. Just
364 as an example, although extreme, we recall the 7 January 2014 storm in the North Atlantic that
365 sent an estimated 15 meter high 18 second swell towards the coast of Ireland, making all the
366 professional surfers of the world rush there to take advantage of the situation.

367

368 Although we have purposely been dealing with seamounts to stress the effects they can have on
369 the surface wave fields, to a large extent, partly at least, our results provide information also for
370 the interaction of ocean waves with islands of limited dimensions and with a suitable
371 surrounding bathymetry. The wake of an island or even an archipelago is a known phenomenon,
372 whose results strictly depend on how one models the situation. In the early time of the WAM
373 wave model (Hasselmann et al., 1986) we came across a case where the wake of the Hawaii
374 islands was unrealistically extending indefinitely South of the archipelago. It was a substantial

375 swell perfectly from the North direction, the bug, soon corrected, was the lack of energy
376 advection from the sides towards the shadowed zone. However, the classical case we have in
377 mind is the typhoon Krosa, 6 October 2007, during which the world record significant and
378 maximum single wave heights were recorded, 23.9 and 32.3 m respectively, see Liu et al., 2008.
379 What is unexpected in reading the paper is that these exceptional data were recorded by a buoy
380 on the lee of an island hit by the maximum strength of the typhoon. The peak significant wave
381 height in front of the island was modeled at about 20 m (Babanin et al., 2011). A possible
382 explanation is given, as in our examples in Section 4, by the convergence of the two strongly
383 refracted wave systems on both sides of the island.

384

385 We close with a less technical, but perhaps more interesting, note. When we, modern and
386 technological people, dig into a natural subject and come across unexpected results, we may feel
387 a sense of satisfaction, and even some complacency with ourselves for “discovering” the secrets
388 of nature. Possibly this is not the case here, but, for the subject we have been dealing with, it is
389 interesting to explore a bit the ancient art of navigation in the Pacific islands (Polynesia,
390 Micronesia, Solomon, etc.). A good reference book is “We, the navigators” by David Lewis,
391 1994. The local people used to navigate hundreds of kilometers from island to island, these
392 mostly visible only when very close to them, without any modern instrument, relying only on
393 reading the stars in the sky and “literally reading” the waves. Obviously with a previous
394 knowledge of the general local (but not very local) conditions, they were able to derive with
395 amazing accuracy their position, looking, often not by eye, but by direct feeling, the locally
396 present wave systems. Two similar wave system, coming at a certain angle, could identify the
397 presence of an island in the up-swell direction, its distance suggested (remember our Figure 7,
398 panels g and h) by the angle between the two swells. No doubt the modern technology has
399 brought to us a wealth of fantastic tools. However, we feel that at the same time the capability of
400 solving (some of) the problems of nature with only our inner and learned knowledge should not
401 be lost.

402

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404

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409

410 **References**

411

412 Babanin, A.V., T.-W.Hsu, A.Roland, S.-H.Ou, D.-J.Doong, and C.C.Kao, 2011. Spectral wave
413 modelling of Typhoon Krosa, *Nat. Hazards Earth Syst. Sci.*, **11**, 501–511

414

415 Babanin, A., Young, I., Mirfenderesk, H., 2005: Field and Laboratory Measurements of Wave-
416 bottom Interaction. Conference Proceedings Coasts and Ports 2005, Australia: 293-298. ISBN:
417 0646451308.

418

419 Booij, N., L.H.Holthuijsen, and R.C.Ris, 1996, The SWAN wave model for shallow water, Proc.
420 25th Int. Conf. Coastal Engng., Orlando, USA, Vol. **1**, pp. 668-676.

421

422 Chen, G., D.Wang, C.Dong, T.Zu, H.Xue, Y.Shu, X.Chu, Y.Qi, and H.Chen, 2015. Observed
423 deep energetic eddies by seamount wake, *Nature – Scientific Reports*, 5 17416, DOI
424 10.1038/srep17416.
425

426 Davidson-Arnott, R., 2009, *Introduction to Coastal Processes and Geomorphology*. Cambridge,
427 UK: Cambridge University Press, 458 pp., ISBN 978-0521696715
428

429 French, S:W., and B.Romanowicz, 2015. Broad plumes rooted at the base of the Earth's mantle
430 beneath major hotspots, *Nature*, 525, 95-99.
431

432 Goda Y., 2009, *Random Seas and Design of Maritime Structures*, Advanced Series on Ocean
433 Engineering, World Scientific, V33, 708 pp., ISBN: 9789814282406
434

435 Hanley M., Hoggart S., Simmonds D., Bichot A., Colangelo M., Bozzeda F., Heurtefeux H.,
436 Ondiviela B., Ostrowski R., Recio M., Trude R., Zawadzka-Kahlau E., Thompson R., 2013,
437 *Shifting sands? Coastal protection by sand banks, beaches and dunes*, *Coastal Engineering*, V87,
438 136-146, doi 10.1016/j.coastaleng.2013.10.020.
439

440 Hasselmann, K., 1962. On the non-linear energy transfer in a gravity-wave spectrum, part 1:
441 general theory, *J.Fluid Mech*, **12**, 481
442

443 Holthuijsen, L.H., 2007. *Waves in oceanic and coastal waters*, Cambridge University Press, 404
444 pp., ISBN: 9780521129954.
445

446 Jackson, L.A., Tomlinson, R.B., Turner, I., Corbett, B., D'Agata, M. and McGrath, J., 2005
447 *Narrowneck Reef: Results of 4 years monitoring and modifications*, 4th Int Surfing Reef
448 Symposium, Los Angeles, January 2005.
449

450 Kearey P., Klepeis K., Vine F., 2009, *Global Tectonics 3rd Edition*, Wiley-Blackwell, 496 pp.,
451 ISBN 9781405107778.
452

453 Keating, B. H., Fryer, P., Batiza, R. and Boehlert, G. W., 1987, *Seamounts, Islands, and Atolls*,
454 *Geophysical Monograph Series V43*, American Geophysical Union, Washington, D. C. 405 pp.,
455 ISBN 978-0875900681
456

457 Langhamer O., Haikonen K., Sundberg J., 2010, *Wave power—Sustainable energy or*
458 *environmentally costly? A review with special emphasis on linear wave energy converters*,
459 *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, V14-4, 1329-1335, doi 10.1016/j.rser.2009.11.016.
460

461 Lewis, D., 1994. *We the navigators: the ancient art of landfinding in the Pacific*, 2 Ed., 468 pp.,
462 ISBN: 978-0824815820
463

464 Liu, P.C., H.S.Chen, D.-J.Doong, and Y.-J.G.Hsu, 2008. Monstrous ocean waves during typhoon
465 Krosa, *Ann. Geophys.*, **26**, 1327–1329.

466
467 Nielsen P., 2009: Coastal and Estuarine Processes, Advanced Series on Ocean Engineering,
468 World Scientific, V29, 343 pp., ISBN: 9789812837127
469
470 Pierson, W.J., and W.Marks, 1952. The power spectrum analysis of ocean-wave records, *Earth*
471 *and Space Science News*, **33**, Issue 6, 834-844.
472
473 Short, A., Woodroffe, C., 2009. The Coast of Australia. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press,
474 288 p. ISBN 978-0521873987
475
476 Sinton, J., 1989, Evolution of Mid Ocean Ridges, Geophysical Monograph Series, V57,
477 American Geophysical Union, 77 pp. ISBN 9780875904580.
478
479 Wessel P., Sandwell D., Kim S., 2010. The global seamount census, *Oceanography*, 23, 24–33.
480
481 Yesson C., Clark M., Taylor M., Rogers A., 2011, The global distribution of seamounts based on
482 30 arc seconds bathymetry data, *Deep Sea Research Part I: Oceanographic Research Papers*,
483 V58-4, 442-453, doi 10.1016/j.dsr.2011.02.004.
484